

THERMAL EVOLUTION OF THE LUNAR MAGMA OCEAN CONTROLLED BY TIDAL HEATING.

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Introduction: The timing of the Lunar Magma Ocean (LMO) crystallization is governed by its thermal evolution. Under simple convective cooling, the LMO would have cooled and completely solidified very rapidly (<1 Ma) if the energy budget were dominated by radiogenic heating [1]. However, analyses of lunar samples show that all LMO products record ages, or age peaks, clustered near 4.35 ± 0.05 Ga (Fig. 2) [2], a delay of over 100 Ma from Moon formation at ~ 4.50 Ga. This discrepancy raises two fundamental questions regarding LMO evolution:

(1) How did the LMO remain hot for more than 100 Myr prior to its final solidification?

(2) After such a prolonged delay, how could the final solidification occur so rapidly, within only tens of Myr?

Several mechanisms have been proposed to reconcile the young ages of LMO products (e.g., ferroan anorthosites and Mg-suite rocks). These hypotheses can be broadly grouped into two classes: (1) slow cooling of the LMO, leading to late solidification [1, 3]. This scenario would predict a prolonged and sequential distribution of crystallization ages, rather than the tightly clustered ages that are observed; and (2) remelting followed by re-crystallization, triggered by catastrophic events such as the South Pole–Aitken (SPA) basin impact or the Laplace Plane Transition (LPT) [4, 5]. However, this class of models requires finely tuned timing and involves large uncertainties regarding the extent and global thermal consequences of such events.

Here we propose that the intrinsic rheological changes in an evolving magma ocean produce enhanced tidal heating that explains both the delay and rapid final solidification of the LMO. As the LMO crystallizes, its tidal response evolves in a manner that can strongly amplify dissipation within a transitional regime. In this framework, (1) tidal heating within the LMO itself can dominate the energy budget for an extended interval, thereby delaying crystallization, and (2) the subsequent decay of tidal forcing, together with the exit from the transitional rheology, can drive a rapid late-stage shutdown, producing a thermal “cliff” consistent with the observed ~ 4.35 Ga age cluster. The underlying physical mechanisms and the coupled thermal–orbital modeling are outlined below.

Mechanisms. Tidal heating converts orbital/rotational energy into internal heat through cyclic deformation. Its magnitude depends on two ingredients: the external forcing exerted by Earth and the Moon’s frequency-dependent mechanical re-

sponse [6]. During the LMO epoch the Earth–Moon distance was far smaller than at present, implying much stronger forcing (with a strong distance dependence). Nonetheless, strong forcing alone does not guarantee large dissipation: if the Moon behaves

Fig. 1. Geochronology of LMO products. Filled circles represent ages of mare source regions, ferroan anorthosites, urKREEP, and Mg-suite rocks; the grey background denotes detrital zircon ages. Data are from [2]. The red curve shows the evolution of LMO tidal heating for an example case. Numbers enclosed in black squares indicate the four evolutionary stages discussed in the Results sec-

as a stiff, nearly elastic body, strain amplitudes and phase lags remain small, and heating is weak. The assumption of a stiff lunar interior underlies many earlier estimates that found limited lunar tidal dissipation, but during LMO solidification, the Moon would have been much weaker.

While a fully molten LMO has low viscosity and low tidal dissipation, crystallization drives viscosity upward by many orders of magnitude. Both endmembers—very low viscosity melt and very high viscosity solid—dissipate inefficiently (the former because shear stresses are small; the latter because deformation is largely elastic). Maximum dissipation occurs at intermediate viscosities, when the viscoelastic relaxation timescale becomes comparable to the relevant tidal period (Fig. 1). As the LMO cools into this transitional window, tidal heating increases rapidly until it matches surface heat loss, yielding a thermally self-regulating, stable state. The LMO exits this stable state when the Moon recedes far enough for the Moon to cool to the high-viscosity side of the dissipation curve, where heating decreases with increasing viscosity; the balance then becomes unstable, and the magma ocean undergoes a rapid cooling/solidification episode.

More generally, tidally heated magma oceans tend to linger near a sequence of stable thermal states and traverse the unstable segments quickly, producing long delays followed by abrupt late-stage shut-down. This generic behavior aligns with the geochronologic signature of LMO products—both the extended pre-solidification interval (stable state) and the subsequent rapid final crystallization (unstable state). Similar feedback has been explored for Io, icy satellites, and exoplanets [7], but has rarely been considered in the context of LMO.

Fig. 2. Variation of LMO tidal heating (red) and surface heat-loss (cooling) rates (blue) as functions of temperature and melt fraction. The green trajectory indicates the evolutionary path of LMO tidal heating, governed by stable and unstable thermal equilibria. More details in [8].

Methods: We developed a coupled thermal–orbital zero-dimensional model of the Moon from ~ 4.5 to 4.0 Ga, in which the LMO is treated as a spatially homogeneous box, focusing on the transitional rheology stage of the LMO, following tidal-heating formulations developed for Io and exoplanets [7]. Key components include:

(1) A parameterized thermal framework for LMO cooling, accounting for convective and conductive heat loss.

(2) Rheology controlled tidal dissipation, implemented by coupling a temperature- and melt-fraction-dependent viscosity law to a frequency-dependent viscoelastic formulation for tidal heating.

(3) Coupled Earth–Moon orbital evolution, where Earth’s tidal response (Q/k_2) governs lunar recession and the decay of tidal forcing.

Results: Across the explored orbital parameter space, our model produces a high energy thermal plateau (stable equilibrium) followed by a thermal cliff (unstable equilibrium) in LMO tidal heating. LMO tidal heating (~ 500 – 30 TW) can exceed radiogenic heating (~ 1.8 – 1.4 TW) by more than an order of magnitude. Taking the case of an eccentricity of 0.05 and Earth’s $Q/k_2 = 400$ as an example (results in

Fig. 2), the thermal evolution of the LMO separates into four stages:

(1) *Early rapid cooling*, with negligible tidal heating; the LMO drops to a melt fraction of $\phi \approx 0.6$ within 1 Myr and convective heat loss exceeds ~ 500 TW.

(2) *Stable equilibrium*, where tidal dissipation rises to the hundreds-of-TW level and balances cooling as the system traverses the transitional rheology window.

(3) *Thermal cliff*, near 4.35 Ga, when the equilibrium becomes unstable and tidal heating falls below radiogenic heating within <30 Myr.

(4) *Secular slow cooling*, where low tidal heating leaves radiogenic heating as the primary buffer.

The cliff age depends on orbital forcing (eccentricity and Earth-controlled recession), spanning ~ 4.50 – 3.50 Ga across our parameter search, with multiple combinations yielding 4.35 ± 0.05 Ga (more results in Zhao et al. [8]).

Conclusions: Our coupled thermal–orbital model shows that tidal dissipation within the LMO, amplified during the liquid-like to solid-like rheological transition, can dominate the lunar energy budget for an extended interval. This produces a long-lived thermal plateau followed by a rapid thermal cliff, reconciling both the >100 Myr delay and the subsequent rapid final solidification implied by the clustered $\sim 4.35 \pm 0.05$ Ga ages of LMO products. The timing of the cliff is controlled primarily by orbital forcing, yielding a range of solutions across parameter space consistent with ~ 4.35 Ga. A first-order nearside–farside correction further predicts a short-lived late-stage hemispheric thermal contrast (asymmetric results are presented in a companion abstract by Parman et al.). More broadly, this framework implies that tidal heating may have influenced lunar thermal evolution on longer timescales, potentially contributing to the persistence of mare volcanism and the evolution of the lunar dynamo.

A preprint of this work is available on arXiv (arXiv:2511.19946). This work was supported by LunaSCOPE, NASA SSERVI grant 80NSSC23M0161.

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